

Structural Equation Model on Organization Communication Satisfaction of Hotel Employees in Region XII

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to develop the best fit model on organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees using structural equation modelling (SEM) as the fundamental statistical tool to analyse the interrelationship among the constructs of organizational efficacy, service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction. It employed descriptive-correlational research design and used stratified-random sampling technique in choosing the 402 hotel employees. Mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation, Multiple Regression and Structural Equation Modelling were applied as statistical tools to the levels, interrelationships, influence, and explored the best fit model of the constructs respectively. Significant relationships of the three constructs with organization communication satisfaction were established. Organizational efficacy and service climate were always observed while social exchanged and organization communication satisfaction were sometimes observed by the respondents. When regressed, it was found that service climate and social exchange influenced organization communication satisfaction. The best fit model of organization communication satisfaction is model 5. The model showed that organizational efficacy as indicated by sense of resilience and social exchange as indicated by experiential information, emotional support, humour exchanged and exchange outside meetings best predict organization communication satisfaction as indicated by organizational integration, supervisor communication and media quality.

Keywords: *management organizational efficacy, service climate, social exchange organization communication satisfaction, SEM, Philippines.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Communication plays a significant role in informative transmission within any organization. A leader of an organization needs to be pleased with the communication practices in his organization, in order to work effectively (Saurabh et al 2013). Communication is the sustenance of any organisation and the success of a business enterprise to a great extent will depend upon the efficient and effective communication (Bisen&Priya, 2008). It is also seen as one of the most important issues for administrators and workers in the workplace (Cascio, 2000).

As cited by Kaul (2017) in his article, the statements of Robert Kent, previous dean of Harvard Business School, that in business, communication is so important. It is often called a soft skill communication offers an crucial link between and among all fundamental functions in an organization. When administration had commendably engaged in all types of written and oral communication, the organization develops its profitability and credibility within the business community. This is affirmed by Wyatt (2004), that the key driver of superior performance were connections and favourable organization-employee relationships.

Organization communication satisfaction is worthy to be investigated (Tsai, Chuang, & Hsieh, 2009). The level of communication satisfaction where supervisors and managers are open to suggestions, listen and pay attention, and have guidance to address job-related problems and feedback.

As reported in Malekane's study (2014), he found out that in order for an organization to use its purpose to its best possible level, good internal communication features often need to be worked out with employee satisfaction and communication efficiency. The combinations between these activities ensure that employers and employees are considerate about the vision of the organization where it is heading. However, contact satisfaction of workplace organizations in global companies remains unexplored (Snape and Redman, 2010). Employees are said to be one of the core factors in the effective operation of the hospitality sector, driving competitive advantages in the hotel industry. If the company has the right staff, the probability of success for any firm can be significantly improved (Connor, et.al., 2003; Karatepe et al., 2009).

In Hong, et.al. (2013) research, organizations are advised to promote a positive service environment as it directs employee attitudes and behaviors and is a key factor in organizational success (Kusluvanet.al., 2010). Service climate study, however, has focused heavily on assessing the perceptions of customers (Bowen and Schneider, 2014), their satisfaction, and the effect on the financial performance of the business.

Service workers who have encountered positive leadership (supervisor support) and participant (co-worker support in the same team and interdepartmental support), relationships are likely to experience a higher degree of support, resulting in greater commitment to organizational objectives (Snape and Redman, 2010). Co-worker support, inter-departmental support and supervisor support collected can be perceived as internal customer service. The main assertion from the Social Exchange Theory (SET) is that a firm's partnership relationships are a social exchange network.

Based on these discussions, organization communication satisfaction still remain unexplored, hence, there should be a further research to be conducted on the relationships between and among other organizational issues that either positively or negatively affect the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees.

It is on the above context that the researcher decided to conduct the study dealing with the three variables as a construct of organization communication satisfaction. While there are existing studies on the link of each mentioned variable to organization communication satisfaction, those studies are in bivariate relationships only and conducted separately by different researchers.

This study, however, is a superior version of those individual studies considering that it covers the four variables in the study with the hope of producing a model for organization communication satisfaction specifically for hotel employees making this study will become a meaningful contribution to new knowledge, hence the conduct of this study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

This study employed quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlational technique. This is used to develop and employ mathematical models, theories and or hypothesis pertaining to a phenomenon. In the extraction of the best fit model, structural equation model was used. First, it utilized descriptive correlational method. According to Gill (2013), a descriptive study entails describing a certain aspect of a group of individuals whose responses are continuous data where simple means on the average level is depicted. On one hand, correlation is used to investigate and measure the connection between two or more variables.

The study used structural equation modelling that aims to come up with the best fit model on organization communication satisfaction that may help hotel businesses attract, select and retain employees. This is a multivariate technique to scrutinize multiple dependence relationships among the variables at the same time (Bose, 2019). Specifically, this research examined the interrelationship of organizational efficacy, service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction among hotel employees.

Structural equation modelling is a complex method of data analysis as compared to other statistical method. It is a mathematical tool used for delineating causal conclusions from a fusion of observational data and theoretical assumptions (Bhatta, Albert, Kahana&Lekhak, 2017; Hair, Babin&Krey, 2017; Pearl, 2012).

This study used the normal theory methods in the parameter estimates due to the large sample to have asymptotically biased, efficient and consistent due to sample estimate convergence (Tomarken, 2005).

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the SOCSKSARGEN Region, designated as Region XII, one of the regions in the Philippines situated in the central portion of Mindanao. It is consisted of four provinces, namely: South Cotabato, Sultan Kudarat, Sarangani and North Cotabato.

The respondents of this study were the hotel employees in Region XII specifically from General Santos City, Koronadal City, Tacurong City, Kidapawan City and Isulan, Sultan Kudarat. Survey questionnaires were administered in the said areas.

As of this writing, hotel employees in Region XII can take any challenges, can work effectively with groups to accomplish a goal, responds to customer' feedback and suggestions quickly. Supervisors and employees were optimistic to accomplish their goals.

Population and Sample

Scientific process was employed in choosing the respondents. Stratified-random sampling was used in determining the respondents. A random sample was done where participants of the population were first divided into strata, then they are randomly selected to be a part of the sample (Boodie, 2018). A total of 402 completed surveys were made which was way higher than the maximum number of 400 at 0.05 significance level (Davis and Cosenza 2005). Respondents of the study were the existing employees from hotel establishments in Region XII. Of the 402 respondents, 100 were from General Santos City, 95 from Koronadal City, 80 from Tacurong City, 65 from Kidapawan City, and 62 from Isulan, Sultan Kudarat.

Employees who have rendered of at least three (3) months of service in the industry were considered as respondents. On other hand, those newly appointed employees with less than three (3) months of service as well as with those outside the locale of the study were excluded. Respondents can withdraw anytime he/she feels uncomfortable, intimidated or there is actual and perceived threat physically, psychologically, or emotionally.

Data gathering was conducted from October, 2019 to November 2019.

Research Instrument

Primary data were used in gathering data about the study constructs which include organization communication satisfaction, organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange. The survey questionnaires utilized was sourced from various related researches with some modification to fit in the respondents of the study. Restructuring was carried out to make the instrument more applicable to current local business setting.

The survey on organizational efficacy was adapted from Bohn (2001). The said instrument was designed to measure the organizational efficacies of hotels based on three factors, namely: collective capability, sense of mission and sense of resilience. The responses of study participants are interpreted using

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very High	This means that the organizational efficacy is always observed
3.40-4.19	High	This means that the organizational efficacy is oftentimes observed
2.60-3.39	Moderate	This means that the organizational efficacy is sometimes observed
1.8-2.59	Low	This means that the organizational efficacy is rarely observed
1.0 - 1.79	Very Low	This means that the organizational efficacy is not observed

The survey instrument on service climate was adapted from the study of He, et.al. (2010). The instrument was designed to measure the service climate as perceived by hotel employees based on three factors, namely; customer orientation, managerial support and work facilitation. Responses of study participants are interpreted using the scale below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.2-5.00	Very High	This means that the service climate is always observed
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the service climate is oftentimes observed
2.60 -3.39	Moderate	This means that the service climate is sometimes observed
1.8 - 2.59	Low	This means that the service climate is rarely observed
1.0 - 1.79	Very Low	This means that the service climate is not observed

The survey instrument on social exchange was adapted from the study of Brown et al (2014). The instrument was designed to measure the social exchange as perceived by hotel employees based on the four indicators, as emotional support, experiential information, humor exchanged, and exchange outside meetings. The responses of study participants are interpreted using the scale below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.2 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the social exchange is always observed
3.40- 4.19	High	This means that the social exchange is oftentimes observed
2.60 -3.39	Moderate	This means that the social exchange is sometimes observed
1.80 - 2.59	Low	This means that the social exchange is rarely observed
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	This means that the social exchange is not observed

The survey instrument in Organization communication satisfaction was adapted from the study of Iyer et al (2012) based on five indicators, organization integration, personal feedback, communication climate, supervisor communication and media quality. The responses of study participants are interpreted using the scale below:

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.2 - 5.00	Very High	This means that organization communication satisfaction is always observed.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that organization communication satisfaction is oftentimes observed.
2.60 -3.39	Moderate	This means that organization communication satisfaction is sometimes observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	This means that organization communication satisfaction is rarely observed.
1.00- 1.79	Very Low	This means that organization communication satisfaction is seldom observed.

Data Collection

Several procedures were performed in collecting the data used in the study. The first procedure was the acquisition of consent to administer the study. It was secured from the University Of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) last October 15, 2019. After the receipt of a certification from U MERC, the researcher conducted a pilot testing of the questionnaires to three hotel establishments in Tacurong City which was validated by five expert validators with an overall rating of 3.905 or Good. After validation, pilot testing was conducted. Cronbach alpha was used to check the validity of the questionnaire with the following measures: organizational efficacy (0.947), service climate (0.948), social exchange (0.960) and organization communication satisfaction (0.966). The Cronbach's alpha consistency coefficient customarily ranges between zero to one. However, there was no lower limit to the coefficient. The closer the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to one, the larger the internal consistency of the items in the scale (Gliem & Gliem 2003).

Moreover, Darren and Mallery (1999) postulated these rules of thumb in measuring questionnaire's reliability using Cronbach's alpha: if the result is greater than or equal to 0.9 it is excellent; greater than or equal to 0.8 is good; greater than or equal to 0.7 is acceptable; greater than or equal to 0.6 is questionable; greater than or equal to 0.5 is poor and greater than or equal to 0.4 is unacceptable.

A total of 41 retrieved questionnaires were pilot tested. Responses were tallied and determined its validity. Reproduction of survey questionnaires was facilitated from October to November, 2019. Approved request letters signed by the adviser and the dean of graduate school were distributed together with the questionnaires to the selected hotel establishments in region XII specifically in the areas of General Santos City, Koronadal City, Tacurong City, Kidapawan City and in Isulan, Sultan Kudarat. Then a time table was set for the duration of the floating and retrieval of questionnaires which was from October 15 until November 10, 2019. Gradual administration and retrieval of data, collation and tabulation of data was conducted wherein data screening was done to eliminate the outliers during the analysis. And lastly, analysis and interpretation of data, wherein results were analysed and interpreted.

Statistical Tools

The data collected were analysed and evaluated using the following statistical tools:

Mean. This was employed to ascertain the level of organizational efficacy, service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was utilized to establish the connectivity between organizational efficacy, service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction.

Multiple Regression. This was employed to reveal the significant predictors of organization communication satisfaction.

Structural Equation Modelling. This study requires the use of SEM to explore the best fit model. The essence of the test according to Savalei and Bentler (2010) is to confirm the exclusion of attributes with low relationships with the attributes of the other latent factors in the final SEM.

III. RESULTS

This chapter presents the data and deconstruction of findings based on the responses of the respondents on the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees in Region XII. The discussions were sequenced according to the following sub-headings: level of organizational efficacy, level of service climate, level of social exchange and level of organization communication satisfaction. It is followed by a regression analysis on the influence of organizational efficacy and organization communication satisfaction, service climate and organization communication satisfaction. And lastly, the best fit model that predicts the organization communication satisfaction. It can be gathered from the data that standard deviation is below 1.00. This shows the consistency of responses (Reiners, et al., 2018).

Level of Organizational Efficacy of Hotels

Shown in Table 1 is the level of organizational efficacy of hotels in Region XII. The overall mean score obtained on the organizational efficacy is 4.28 with a standard deviation of 0.51, described as very high. This means that the

organizational efficacy of hotels is always observed. Specifically, the three indicators got a very high description and the mean ratings are disclosed as follows: collective capability attained a mean rating of 4.35; sense of mission and future obtained a mean rating of 4.23; and sense of resilience got a mean rating of 4.25. The overall very high response of hotel employees means that the domain of organizational efficacy are always observed.

Table 1

Level of Organizational Efficacy of Hotels

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Collective Capability	0.57	4.35	Very high
Sense of Mission and Future	0.61	4.23	Very high
Sense of Resilience	0.55	4.25	Very high
Overall	0.51	4.28	Very high

Level of Service Climate of Hotel Employees

Depicted in Table 2 is the summary of the level of service climate of hotel employees. The overall mean score is 4.24 with standard deviation of 0.52, described as “very high” which means that service climate is always observed by the respondents.

The mean ratings of the indicators of service climate are unveiled as follows: customer orientation landed a mean rating of 4.28 or very high; managerial support acquired a mean rating of 4.27 or very high; and work facilitation rounded up a mean rating of 4.16 or high.

Table 2

Level of Service Climate of Hotels

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Customer Orientation	0.59	4.28	Very high
Managerial Support	0.62	4.27	Very high
Work Facilitation	0.61	4.16	High
Overall	0.52	4.24	Very high

Level of Social Exchange of Hotel Employees

Presented in Table 3 is the level of social exchange of hotel employees in Region XII. The overall mean rating is 3.54 with a standard deviation 0.65, described as “high” which means that social exchange is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

The mean score of the indicators of social exchange are conveyed as follows: experiential information earned a mean of 3.38 or moderate; emotional support garnered a mean rating of 3.82 or high; humor exchanged got a mean of 3.62 or high and exchange outside meetings gained a mean rating of 3.33 or moderate.

Table 3

Level of Social Exchange

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Experiential Information	0.91	3.38	Moderate
Emotional Support	0.77	3.82	High
Humor exchanged	0.81	3.62	High
Exchange Outside Meetings	0.86	3.33	Moderate
Overall	0.65	3.54	High

Level of Organizational Communication Satisfaction of Hotel Employees

Indicated in Table 4 is the level of organizational organization satisfaction of hotel employees in Region XII. The overall mean score is 4.12 with a standard deviation of 0.62, described as high which means that personality dimension is oftentimes observed by the respondents.

The mean rating of the indicators of organization communication satisfaction are elaborated as follows: organization integration and supervisor communication got mean ratings of 4.20 and 4.23 respectively, of which both were described as very high. Personal feedback, communication climate and media quality attained a high description, where these indicators garnered a mean ratings of 3.97, 4.10, and 4.09 respectively.

Table 4

Level of Organizational Communication Satisfaction

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Organization Integration	0.66	4.20	Very high
Supervisor Communication	0.74	4.23	Very high
Personal Feedback	0.80	3.97	High
Communication Climate	0.73	4.10	High
Media Quality	0.71	4.09	High
Overall	0.62	4.12	High

Correlation between Organizational Efficacy and Organization Communication Satisfaction

Table 5.1 displays the data on the results of correlations between organizational efficacy and organization communication satisfaction. The overall r-value attained by the aforesaid measures is 0.518 with a p-value less than 0.05 is significant yet in moderate level (Evans, 1996), still rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

Moreover, it was observed that organizational integration, supervisor communication, personal feedback, communication climate and media quality as indicators of organization communication satisfaction when correlated to collective Capability sense of mission and future and sense of Resilience, the overall value are 0.429, 0.471 and 0.496 respectively with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant.

Table 5.1

Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Efficacy and Organization Communication Satisfaction

Organizational Efficacy	Organization Communication Satisfaction					Overall
	Organizational Integration	Supervisor Communication	Personal Feedback	Communication Climate	Media Quality	
Collective Capability	.354** (.000)	.337** (.000)	.434** (.000)	.449** (.000)	.246** (.000)	.429** (.000)
Sense of Mission and andFuture	.372** (.000)	.345** (.000)	.480** (.000)	.490** (.000)	.307** (.000)	.471** (.000)
Sense of Resilience	.372** (.000)	.445** (.000)	.466** (.000)	.492** (.000)	.325** (.000)	.496** (.000)
Overall	.408** (.000)	.417** (.000)	.513** (.000)	.531** (.000)	.326** (.000)	.518** (.000)

Correlations between Service Climate and Organization Communication Satisfaction

Table 5.2 exhibits the data on the results of correlations between service climate and organization communication satisfaction. The overall r-value obtained from the said measures is 0.641 with a p-value of less than 0.05 which is lesser than .05 level of significance. The result is a very strong. Significant level (Evans, 1996), hence the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Table 5.2

Significance on the Relationship between Service Climate and Organization Communication Satisfaction

Service Climate	Organization Communication Satisfaction					Overall
	Organizational Integration	Supervisor Communication	Personal Feedback	Communication Climate	Media Quality	
Customer Orientation	.465** (.000)	.450** (.000)	.413** (.000)	.519** (.000)	.408** (.000)	.528** (.000)
Managerial Support	.466** (.000)	.454** (.000)	.425** (.000)	.439** (.000)	.399** (.000)	.512** (.000)
Work Facilitation	.521** (.000)	.521** (.000)	.545** (.000)	.568** (.000)	.490** (.000)	.622** (.000)
Overall	.560** (.000)	.550** (.000)	.534** (.000)	.589** (.000)	.500** (.000)	.641** (.000)

Furthermore, it was observed that customer orientation, managerial support, and work facilitation as indicators of service climate when correlated to organization integration, the overall r-value is 0.560 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. When the indicators of service climate are correlated to supervisor communication, the overall r-value is 0.550 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. When indicators of service climate are correlated to personal feedback, the overall r-value is 0.534 with $p < 0.05$, hence significant.

Finally, as the indicators of service climate are correlated to communication climate and media quality, they garnered an overall r-value of 0.589 and 0.500 respectively with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. All the probability values indicated significant correlations.

Correlations between Social Exchange and Organization Communication Satisfaction

Table 5.3 shows the data on the results of correlations between social exchange and organization communication satisfaction. The overall r-value is 0.455 with $p < 0.05$ which is significant rejecting the null hypothesis of no significant relationship.

Further, it was observed that organization integration, supervisor communication, personal feedback, communication climate and media quality as indicators of organization communication satisfaction when correlated to experiential information, the overall r-value is 0.268 with $p < 0.5$ hence, significant. Likewise, when indicators of organization communication satisfaction are correlated to emotional support, the overall r-value is 0.466 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Moreover, when indicators of organization communication satisfaction were correlated to humor exchanged, the overall r-value is 0.299 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. Lastly, when indicators of organization communication satisfaction were correlated to exchange outside meetings, the overall r-value is 0.380 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. The probability values showed significant correlations.

Table 5.3

Significance on the Relationship between Social Exchange and Organization Communication

Social Exchange	Organization Communication Satisfaction					Overall
	Organizational Integration	Supervisor Communication	Personal Feedback	Communication Climate	Media Quality	
Experiential Information	.164** (.001)	.193** (.000)	.390** (.000)	.200** (.000)	.173** (.001)	.268** (.000)
Emotional Support	.385** (.000)	.382** (.000)	.479** (.000)	.350** (.000)	.381** (.000)	.466** (.000)
Humor Exchanged	.223** (.000)	.269** (.000)	.242** (.000)	.262** (.000)	.278** (.000)	.299** (.000)
Exchange Outside Meetings	.282** (.000)	.247** (.000)	.468** (.000)	.359** (.000)	.267** (.000)	.380** (.000)
Overall	.331** (.000)	.349** (.000)	.513** (.000)	.377** (.000)	.351** (.000)	.455** (.000)

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Influence of Organizational Efficacy, Service Climate and Social Exchange on Organization Communication Satisfaction

Presented in Table 6 is the analysis of organization communication satisfaction as regressed on organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange. The regression analysis shows how changes in the organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange are associated with changes in the organization communication satisfaction.

Results of the analysis revealed that around 47.6 or 48% of the variation on the organization communication satisfaction is attributed to service climate and social exchange. It can be noted that for every unit of service climate, while holding social exchange constant, is increased by 0.51. Similarly, for every unit of social exchange, as service climate remains as it is, organizational communication satisfaction is increased by 0.26.

However, organizational efficacy may like have no contribution on the organization communication satisfaction. This is evident on its t-value of 1.208 with p-value of 0.228 which is greater than 0.05.

The result shows further that service climate and social exchange have significant influence with organization communication satisfaction, hence the null hypothesis of no significant influence is rejected.

It can be gleaned that results revealed a good model as indicated by F= 114.75 with a p-value of 0.000.

Table 6

Significance on the Influence of Exogenous Variables on the Organization Communication Satisfaction

Organization Communication Satisfaction				
Exogenous Variables	B	β	t	Sig.
Constant	.358		1.683	.093
Organizational Efficacy	.078	.064	1.208	.228
Service Climate	.603	.508	9.697	.000
Social Exchange	.246	.257	6.338	.000
R	.690			
R ²	.476			
ΔR	.472			
F	114.750			
p	.000			

*p<.05

Best Fit Model of Organization Communication Satisfaction

This section highlights the analysis on the interrelationships among organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange to the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees. There are five alternative models tested to achieve the best fit model of organization communication satisfaction. Each model developed a structure which might be broken down into two sub-models: measurement model and structural model. The measurement model signifies the measure of loads on each factor to their latent constructs while the structural model describes relations among the latent variables. Moreover, the assessment of fit was used as baseline for accepting and rejecting the model. As a rule, the researcher established the relationship of the causality relationship of the latent variable toward the different latent variables.

Furthermore, it constitutes the relationship between the endogenous and exogenous variables. The moment that structured model exhibits with suitable fit, it underscores that there is consistency of the empirical relationships among variables inferred by the model.

There were five hypothesized models formulated and tested in this study. Screening of variables was critically observed to give premium on the normality of the data generated models presented in the study. As shown in the conceptualized models of this study, the direct effects are represented by arrows from a predictor variable illustrated at the right side to the left side where the dependent variables are, without passing through another variable.

The first generated structural model exhibited in the appended figures displayed the direct relationship of the exogenous variables: organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange and its causal relationship on the

endogenous variable which is the organization communication satisfaction. All indices did not reach the acceptable ranges as revealed in the appended tables, hence, a poor fit.

The second generated structural model exhibited in the appended figures showed the interrelationship of the exogenous variables: organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange and its causal relationship on organization communication satisfaction. It could be viewed in the appended tables the direct effects of predictor variables to the dependent variables which is the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees. The model was also found to be a poor fit since all its indices did not reach the acceptable ranges.

The third generated structural model exhibited in appended figures displayed a direct causal interrelationship of exogenous variables service climate and social exchange on organization communication satisfaction. It could be viewed in the appended tables the direct effects of predictor variables to the dependent variable which is the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees. Still all its indices failed to pass the other criterion, thus, model 3 was a poor fit.

The fourth generated structural model exhibited in the appended figures displayed the direct causal interrelationship of the exogenous variables organizational efficacy and social exchange on organization communication satisfaction.

It could be viewed in the appended tables the direct effects of predictor variables to the dependent variable which is the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees. Organizational efficacy obtained the highest total effect of .408 on organization communication satisfaction and followed by the social exchange with .362 effect on organization communication satisfaction. Displayed in the appended tables are the examination of Model 4 using goodness of fit indices. The model was still found not fitting based on the criterion.

Lastly, the generated structural model 5 in standardized solution is a modified version of Model 2 wherein some indicators with low values were removed. Model 5 was found to have indices that consistently indicate a very good fit to the data as all the indices presented fall within each criterion. Thus, there was no need to find another model for testing because it was already found to be the best fit among all the tested model. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no best fit model was rejected. It could be stated that there is indeed a best fit model which the organization predicts communication satisfaction of hotel employees in Region XII.

The model clearly illustrates the importance of organizational efficacy as a predictor of service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees. However, it could be gleaned from the model that out of three variables, only organizational efficacy and social exchange have the direct causal relationships towards organization communication satisfaction.

Organizational efficacy has three (3) indicators, however, only sense of resilience remained as significant predictor of all the variables namely: service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction. For service climate, it is not a good predictor of organization communication of hotel employees but instead, it only retained two out of its three indicators were found to affect social exchange, namely: managerial support and customer orientation.

Social exchange retained its four indicators specifically experiential information, emotional support, humor exchanged and exchange outside meetings as good predictors of organization communication satisfaction. On the part of organization communication satisfaction, it retained only three out of its five indicators namely: organization integration, supervisory communication, and media quality.

Thus, the findings suggest that organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees was best anchored on organizational efficacy which is measured in terms of sense of resilience; and social exchange which is measured in terms of experiential information, emotional support, humor exchanged and exchange outside meetings.

The examination of Model 5 as displayed using goodness of fit indices: Chi-Square divided by the degrees of freedom (MIN/DF) is 1.395; Normed Fit Index (NFI) is .977; Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is .988; Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is .993; Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is .982; Root Means Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA) is .032; and P OF Close Fit (Pclose) is .885. The result of the goodness of fit of the model 5 is highly acceptable since all indices had met the set criterion against the obtained model fit value. These indices satisfied the requirements of the goodness of fit measures. Moreover, this is an indicator that generated model 5 is a very good fit model.

In identifying the best fit model, all indices included must fall within the acceptable ranges. Chi-square/degrees of freedom value should be less than 5 with its corresponding p-value greater than 0.05. The root mean square error approximation value must be less than 0.05 and its corresponding Pclose value must be greater than 0.05. The other indices such as normed fit index, Tucker-Lewis index, comparative fit index and the goodness of fit index must all be greater than 0.95. The five structural models generated in the study were capsulized in Table 7.

Table 7

Direct and Indirect Effects of the Independent Variables on Organization Communication Satisfaction of the Best Fit Model

Direct and Indirect Effects of the Independent Variables on Organization Communication Satisfaction of the Best Fit Model

Variables	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect
Organizational Efficacy	.630	.071	.701
Service Climate	-	.225	.225
Social Exchange	.126	-	.126

Figure 7. The relationships among Organizational Efficacy, Service Climate and Social Exchange and Their Causal Relationship towards Organization Communication Satisfaction.

Legend:

- CO – Customer Orientation
- MS – Managerial Support
- WF – Work Facilitation
- Ser_cli – Service Climate
- EI – Experiential Information
- ES – Emotional Support
- HE – Humor Exchanged
- EM – Exchange Outside Meetings
- OI – Organizational Integration
- SC – Supervisor Communication
- PF – Personal Feedback
- CE – Communication Climate
- MQ – Media Quality
- Org_satt – Organization Communication Satisfaction

Table 8

Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural the Best Fit Model

INDEX	CRITERION	MODEL FIT VALUE
P-Close	> 0.05	.885
CMIN/DF	0 < value < 2	1.395
GFI	> 0.95	.982
CFI	> 0.95	.993
NFI	> 0.95	.977
TLI	> 0.95	.988
RMSEA	< 0.05	.032

Legend:

- CMIN/DF - Chi-Square/Degrees of Freedom
- NFI - Normed Fit Index
- TLI - Tucker-Lewis Index
- CFI - Comparative Fit Index
- GFI - Goodness of Fit Index
- RMSEA - Root Means Squared Error Approximation
- P-close - P of Close Fit

IV. DISCUSSION

Included in this chapter is the discussion of the findings based on the statistical results concerning organizational efficacy, service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees in SOCSKSARGEN region. Discourse on the significance of the relationship and influence of exogenous variables on organization communication satisfaction as well as construct of best fit model on organization communication are comprehensively presented with supporting principles, concepts, ideas and theories which helped to solidify the conclusion and recommendation of the study.

Organizational Efficacy of Hotels

The level of hotels' organizational efficacy is very high. The very high level of organizational efficacy is attributed to all indicators, collective capability, sense of mission and sense of resilience. This means that the organizational efficacy of hotels in region XII is always observed.

The very high level of organizational efficacy of hotels in region XII in terms of collective capability is the result of the very high ratings given to the specific items under organizational efficacy by the respondents and mostly got a

mean rating of 4.30 and above. *People in this organization can take on any challenge; In this organization we can coordinate our efforts to complete difficult projects; People in this organization can work together to accomplish a goal.*

The very high level of organizational efficacy of hotels in Region XII in terms of sense of mission was the result of very highly rated items as follows: *People here have a sense of purpose to accomplish something; Were very certain about what we will accomplish together as a company; and This company has a strong vision.* The sense of resilience as an indicator of organizational efficacy also got a very high level. This means that people in the organization are of full strength and optimism.

The very high level of organizational efficacy of hotels in region XII is an articulation of the pronouncement of Bohn (2010) who stated that organizational efficacy is a combined judgment of an organization's members about their sense of collective skills, sense of mission and sense of resilience. He further stated that organizational efficacy is a generative capacity within an organization to cope effectively with the needs, hurdles, problems and chances it meets in the corporate world. This explains why organizational efficacy obtained a very high rating from the respondents.

Service Climate of Hotels

The level of hotel employees service climate is very high. The very high level of service climate is attributed by customer orientation and managerial support which obtained the highest mean of 4.28 and 4.27 respectively. This means that the service climate of hotel employees in Region XII is always observed.

All items of customer orientation under service climate got a very high level of ratings. The very high level of rating regarded by hotel employees is in consonance with the study of He (2011) where he defined two features of customer orientation which may have a direct influence on customer satisfaction: This is also in congruent to the study of Shainesh and Sharma (2003), that customer orientation is the essential component of the service climate that defines the course and instructions of the company, and the two "wheels" of the carriage, to realize quality service, are managerial support and work facilitation.

The very high level of service climate of hotel employees in Region XII is also primarily due to the managerial support received by them from their supervisors or managers. Three out of four items got a very high level, which means that hotel employees in Region XII always observed the support from their managers or supervisors.

The very high level of service climate in terms of managerial support to hotel employees is confirmed by Liao and Chuang's (2007) who reported that leaders who demonstrated dedication to service quality would demonstrate to their subordinates the value of quality service delivery are highly committed toward improving customer service, they would do the same with their colleagues. Work facilitation is another indicator which attributed to a high level of service climate by hotel employees in Region XII.

All these findings confirms with the researches of Salanova et al (2005); and Schneider and White(2004) which suggested that service climate can be shaped before it can be established.

Social Exchange of Hotel Employees

The level of hotel employees social exchange is high. Such result is attributed by two out of four indicators: Emotional Support and Humor Exchanged. This means that the social exchange of hotel employees in region XII is oftentimes observed. These activities are an articulation of the pronouncements of Szabo, Ainsworth, & Danks (2005) as reductions in anxiety, and better moods of hopefulness (Vilaythong, Arnau, Rosen, and Mascaro 2003).

Organization Communication Satisfaction of Hotel Employees

The level of organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees in region XII is high. Two out of five indicators got a very high rating such as: organization integration and supervisor communication. This means that organization communication of hotel employees in region XII is highly satisfied.

The remaining three indicators which obtained a high level of rating are: personal feedback, communication climate and media quality.

These actions therefore are likely to increase the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees in region XII since it is congruent to the views of Mount and Back's(1999) research studies related to the piloted hotel workers.

In addition, Akkirmanand Harris(2005) examined the degree of organizational communicationsatisfaction of modern employees and traditional office workers and reported how modern workers are more comfortable with their organizational communication, though they face more difficulties when using technology to interact efficiently with other employees. The very high result of organization communication satisfaction in terms of supervisory communication confirmed with the study of Varona (2002) that communication with supervisors and higher level

managers, the main source of satisfaction were the willingness of supervisor to trust, listen and to accept innovative ideas

Significance on the Relationship between Organizational Efficacy and Organization Communication Satisfaction

There is a significant positive relationship between organization communication satisfaction and organizational efficacy of hotel employees in Region XII. The result is aligned to the findings of Bohn (2010), based from the theory of Bandura.

Social interactions, experiences, and external influences generate organizational beliefs about capability and desired outcomes for a particular activity. A sense of mission operates through the organization's culture providing direction and incentive toward a particular activity.

Significance on the Relationship between Service Climate with Organization Communication Satisfaction

There is also a significant positive correlation of hotel employees' service climate and organization communication satisfaction in Region XII. The findings is congruent to the presumption of Drach-Zahavy and Somech (2013); and Sharma et al 2016), which stated that interactions and mutual assistance amongst service workers is essential for quality of service since The service mechanism is a network of processes focused on interconnections and sub-process interdependence. The significant relationship between service climate and organization communication satisfaction is also reinforced by the results in the study of Liao and Chuang (2004), that customer feedback is often asked for by hotels as a way of customer orientation to have some innovations on organizational performance.

The study of Schneider and White (2004), elaborated that work facilitation as indicator of service climate are resources that are considered as the key to achieving a sense about how well workers are assisted in delivering quality service. Likewise, the study of Steinke (2008) also tested the impact of physical design on service climate and customer outcomes in a context for health treatment context..

Furthermore, a significant relationship between service climate and organization communication is underscored by the study centered on a major University in Australia (Joiner and Bakalis 2006. It is suggested that organizational support may come from supervisors and subordinates, position clarification and resource access that includes similar concept in this.

Significance on the Relationship between Social Exchange and Organization Communication Satisfaction

There is a result of a significant relationship between social exchange and organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees in Region XII. It was observed that organization integration, supervisor communication, personal feedback, communication climate and media quality as indicators in organization communication satisfaction when correlated to experiential information, emotional support, humor exchanged, and exchange outside meetings, as indicators of social exchange showed significant correlations.

Finally, the positive correlation between social exchange and organization communication satisfaction is affirmed in the study of Bohn, (2010), which indicated that communication satisfaction denotes to satisfaction or dissatisfaction which evolved from dealings within a workgroup. This is substantiated by Conrad (1985), that workgroup is the main source for social dealings for a lot of people, the constant communication will offer them the means to represent their sentiments and emotions accomplishing their societal needs.

Multiple Regression Analysis of the Influence of Organizational Efficacy, Service Climate and Social Exchange on Organization Communication Satisfaction

One of the most important purpose of this study is the regression analysis determining the influence of organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange on organization communication satisfaction. It was revealed that organizational efficacy has no significant influence on organization communication satisfaction. However, both service climate and social climate influence organization communication satisfaction.

In the study conducted by Bowen and Schneider (2014) it reveals that service climate focuses on processes relevant to the provision of outstanding services and the degree to which organizational quality of service is

highlighted. This is also reinforced by the results in the study of Liao and Chuang (2004), that feedback from customers is usually asked through cards by hotels as means of customer orientation, for the improvement of hotel performance.

The study of Johnson et al (2015), affirmed that social exchange and organization communication which indicated that communication satisfaction denotes about satisfaction or dissatisfaction coming from social dealings being experienced by employees within a work group. This is substantiated by Fluhmann et al (2012) that interact among employees and managers may lead to a range of benefits which includes enhanced knowledge.

Finally, on Pi, et Al (2008), analysis, Instant Messaging (IM) as the most common electronic media messaging influenced the organizational usage of IM and exploring the relationship between IM and the satisfaction of organizational communication. IM form part of a social exchange and service climate. Results have multiple consequences technology tools positively affect the organized communications success and informal communication satisfaction of an organization.

Best Fit Model for Organization Communication Satisfaction

The analysis on the interrelationships among organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange to the organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees in region XII consisted of five models. The models were tested to achieve the best fit model of organization communication satisfaction. Moreover, the assessment of fit was used as baseline for accepting and rejecting the model.

Based on the findings, the model evidently illuminates the essentials of organizational efficacy and social exchange as predictors of organization communication satisfaction. Organizational efficacy and social exchange are important components of organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees to appropriately manage the hotel resources and business as a whole.

Hypothesized model 5 satisfied the criteria for the best fit model. The model apparently showed the importance that one out of three factors of organizational efficacy have direct association with two out of three factors of service climate, complete four factors of socials exchange and three out of five factors of organization communication satisfaction. Service climate only showed a direct association with social exchange and social exchange only have a direct association to organization communication satisfaction.

As shown in the appended level or service climate which resulted to a very high rating, it did not guarantee its influence to organization communication satisfaction as the model was generated, instead, it has an indirect effect.

The best fit model on organization communication satisfaction suggests that hotel employees is best anchored on organizational efficacy which was measured in terms of sense of resilience; service climate which was measured in terms of managerial support and customer orientation; and social exchange which was measured in terms of experiential information, emotional support, humor exchanged and exchanges outside meetings.

Parallel to this, the findings of the study are claimed that resilience was defined as the capacity to rebound or swing back, or the system of reacting to significant stressors like traumatic or disaster, intimate relationship difficulties, serious health issues, or economic troubles (Davidson & Zhang, 2006; Smith, Tooley, Christopher, & Key, (2010); Davidson & Zhang, (2006). Several scholars had described resilience as the recognition of motivating forces inside individual or group which could be linked to favourable results following experiences in challenging life such as development and encouragement called post traumatic development.

The generated best fit model on organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees also conforms to the findings of Iyer and Israel (2012) that organization communication satisfaction have calculated consequences for organizations with greater focus on rising relationship quality by considering various human resource strategies in industries at either the global and local scales.

Conclusion

The use of structural equation model strengthened the rigor of the study because the analysis goes through the steps of model specification, model estimation and model evaluation. Results revealed that the level of organizational efficacy and service climate are very high indicating that these variables are always observed by hotel employees.

There are significant relationships of the following variables: organizational efficacy, service climate and social exchange with organization communication satisfaction congruent with literature as underscored in readings under significance relationships between measures. Of the five models, only model 5 has the indices that consistently indicated an outstanding fit to the data, therefore, it is identified as the best structural model.

As laid down in the Social Exchange Theory (SET), proactive behavior based on workers by the service organizations' members (e.g. service members exceeding personality-interest, love and consideration for clients) would lead to the development of a social atmosphere wherein workers understand and perceive their organizational service climate in a favourable and productive way.

Recommendation

Based on the results of the study, the researcher proposes these recommendations:

The high level rating of social exchange and organization communication satisfaction of hotel employees in regions XII suggest that there is still room for improvement by raising them to a very high level. The human resource department should instigate activities and programs that will improve team works in making wise decision in the organization which will build strong relationships among employees inside and outside the organization.

Improve departmental communications throughout the hotel organizations to foster camaraderie and collaboration among the personnel. Department managers or supervisors have the direct contact with the employees under them, hence, they could facilitate healthy communication environment. This could vouch somehow the employees morale and will motivate them to be more productive.

As a best fit model, organizational efficacy has a strong direct causal effect with service climate, social exchange and organization communication satisfaction, hence, it is recommended that hotel industries will activate continuous programs pertaining to organizational efficacy to sustain strong foundation for the hotel employees to be mission-oriented, technically skilled individuals and resilient to the challenges encountered in the organization. Nurture strong relationship among hotel employees within and outside the organization to foster teamwork and team building.

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